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ADATools for Persistent Scatterer Interferometry based displacement maps analysis: an example in Granada Province (Spain)

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The Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI) technique is being more and more used at all scale's applications. Several regional and national Ground Motions Services based on PSI are nowadays active and operational. The European Ground Motion Service project is going to generate a displacement map over the whole Europe once per year. This context makes indispensable tools and methodologies that facilitate the management and analysis of huge amount of data and information. The ADATools are a set of tools that can be considered a first step in this direction, they are simple and fast tools to firstly extract and make a preliminary interpretation of the main detected Active Deformation Areas (ADA). The ADATools includes: i. the ADAFinder, detecting the main ADA and giving information for each polygon as well as a Quality Index (representing the noise of time series of deformation); ii. the LOS2hv, that is used in case we have datasets from both ascending and descending geometries to derive the horizontal (east-west) and vertical components of the movement; and iii. the ADAClassifier, that makes a preliminary classification of the ADA between landslide, subsidence, settlement, and sinkholes, based on available external data (i.e., DEM, geology, inventories, infrastructures). In this presentation, the algorithm, and performances of the ADATools are presented and some results of their application are showed. Specifically, some results over an area of the Granada Province (S Spain), achieved in the framework of the Project RISKCOAST (funded by the IV Interreg Sudoe Programme through the European Regional Development Fund), will be used to illustrate ADATools performance.